

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE FRAGILITY OF LATIN AMERICA IN THE 21ST CENTURY SEDUCES THE LEFT.

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Abstract

In this article we recreate the scenario of Latin America in the 21st century, where progressive regimes have been seen gaining ground. For example, the triumph of Lula Da Silva in Brazil has an echo in geopolitics for the region, since it not only entails the defeat of the extreme right represented by Jair Bolsonaro also implies the consolidation of a second wave of the left known as the pink tide. We intend to reflect on the role of neoliberal policies that had been the sign of previous administrations, we also analyze the characteristics that political processes and citizen participation assumed. As first findings, discontent with the governments of the day is evident, leading to new ways of thinking about things, politics, society, democracy and history. In conclusion, democracy is a permanent construction that is strengthened with the participation of each member of society; while a new election summons new voters who bring with them a new interpretation of the needs and possibilities offered by democratic systems.

Keywords Latin America, citizenship, left, neoliberal policies.

Introduction.

"...A space for contradiction and encounter, Latin America offers a common field of battle between the cultures of fear and the cultures of freedom, between those that deny us and those that are born to us. That common framework, that common space, that common battlefield, is historical. It comes from the past, feeds on the present and is projected as a need and hope towards the times to come..." (Galeano Eduardo. 2010 -279).

In Latin America at the beginning of the 21st century, the left reappeared on the scene, but it was not the same as that of the sixties or nineties. These new lefts are not Marxists, they are different from each other with their own programs and objectives, which is why they give them different names depending on the reality of each country: neopopulism, new left, and progressivism. Thus, the political map of the region was reconfigured with the governments of Michelle Bachelet, José Mujica, Lula da Silva, Evo Morales and Néstor Kirchner, among others (Raus D. 2022).

In the region, they have seen how the progressive candidacies were imposed in Colombia with Gustavo Petro, in charge of the presidency in Honduras Xiomara Castro and the president of Mexico Andrés Manuel López Obrador among others

We intend to understand the idea of post-neoliberalism and the return of the figure of the State in those scenarios crossed by different social and economic problems. From this perspective, the analysis of political representation and its weaknesses could contribute substantially to the understanding of the return to the left in the region or the search for options that offer a new horizon with concrete measures and actions to the needs of the different nations. . To achieve the proposed objectives, methodological techniques corresponding to the thematic and critical treatment of written documentation will be applied.

Investigation

The pink tide was a wave of leftist governments that began in 1998 with the victory of Hugo Chávez in Venezuela and later continued with the coming to power of candidates such as Lula da Silva in Brazil,

among other regrets of their hybrid condition, these leftist governments shared discontent with the neoliberal policies that dominated the region. Government agendas were reoriented towards the development of policies to promote equality by addressing socio-economic inequalities through greater State intervention in the market and deepening democracy. (Roggeband, C. 2021).

This first pink tide was followed by a short period with right-wing governments, about which we will not go into detail, the political perspectives of Latin America in the first decade of the 21st century are particular, with the exception of Cuba, all the countries in the area are governed by representative democracies, deficiencies are observed in several of them, in some cases they lead to processes of instability between populism and militarism. An example of this is the conflict in Honduras in 2009, *"...where the armed forces deposed the president, Manuel Zelaya, tempted to transgress the constitutional limits of his power by resorting to a referendum that would allow him to extend his mandate and that was not foreseen in the current constitution..."* (Zanatta L. 2016,253-254).

In Brazil, Lula Da Silva at the age of 77, who was president for two terms and imprisoned for corruption, later annulled his conviction. It was imposed by a narrow margin in the 2022 elections, after surpassing Jair Bolsonaro, it is the return of the left to power, thus culminating the most right-wing government in decades, amid ideological antagonisms that divided Brazilian citizens (BBC News World. 2022).

Meanwhile, disgruntled Bolsonaro supporters blocked highways and camped out in front of barracks to protest the results as the defeated president marched on Florida. While Lula gave a speech in which he guaranteed the citizenry that *"...the wheels of our economy will start rolling again, promoting job creation, wage increases and debt renegotiation for those families that have been losing power acquisitive..."* (Singer André. 2023).

Lula y Bolsonaro (Barbieri André 2022).

We could say that we are in the presence of active citizenship since "...the exercise of citizenship rights supposes the recognition of a certain community belonging through which the individual develops and self-determines. At the same time, the process of change that is taking place in this century around the expansion of citizenship, is projected to new dimensions of social positioning, which recognizes its starting point in social rights and advances towards the consolidation of new rights that they operate in a complementary way to guarantee a status of citizen according to the demands of the time..." (Pérez Gamón Carolina 2023).

Meanwhile, Petro defines himself as a leader of the progressive left in a highly traditional and right-wing country. It intends that the economy revolves around the life of Colombians, promoting natural wealth and environmental protection, in addition to creating an economic structure that is based on production and not on extraction, as well as promoting citizen participation in all the realms of democracy. (Loaiza Velásquez 2022).

Andrés Manuel López Obrador (AMLO) current president of Mexico, elected in July 2018, whose mandate will run from December 2018 to 2024, of leftist convictions, committed to the fight against corruption and poverty. In the elections he achieved more than half of the votes, that is, he obtained a vote of more than 53% of the votes, a percentage that guaranteed him a parliamentary majority, unprecedented figures in the recent history of the country. He was elected by the Juntos Haremos Historia coalition, made up of Morena (the party that AMLO founded in 2011, after his break with the PRD), the Labor Party (PT) and the Social Encounter Party (PES). Later, in some regional elections, the Green Ecologist Party of Mexico would join the alliance. The president intends to banish neoliberalism and decentralize the federal government, so far in his administration, López Obrador considers "...it is necessary to continue exposing the great neoliberal farce and banish vices and dishonest practices in government management..." (Regional Agency for News 2022)

First Findings.

We observe that Lula's arrival in the government has vital geopolitical repercussions for the continent, since it not only implies failure for the extreme right embodied by Jair Bolsonaro, but also the consolidation of a second wave of the left, also known as the pink tide, evoking the early of the 2000. At present we observe the own tension between between the citizenship

and the state, between the regulations and the free market.

Conclusions.

In conclusion, the two tendencies mentioned above coexist, despite the fact that one may be stronger than the other. The existence of discontent against the governments of the day, whose origin precedes COVID-19, the pandemic that spread throughout the world, of which progressives are taking advantage today, is evident. On the other hand, the distancing between governments and social movements is lamented, while the latter become the spokesmen for society as a whole. It is necessary to mitigate social inequality not only by fighting poverty but also by reducing it in a sustained manner. Redistributive tax reforms also have a central role and should relieve those who earn less.

In relation to the return to the left, what is happening in the region is the search for options that offer different responses, capable of overcoming social exclusion and alleviating the negative effects of the structural transformations carried out in the stage of neoliberalism without counterweights. The challenge is to advance development models that allow growth to overcome poverty and reduce inequality.

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